

CORRECT CITATIONS OF THE RECENTLY DESCRIBED SPECIES OF GENERA *MERODON*, *CHEILOSIA* AND *PARAGUS* (DIPTERA: SYRPHIDAE)

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Twelve new hoverfly species from Greece and Turkey were described in seven recently published papers: *Merodon longisetus* Vujić, Radenković et Likov, 2020 (Likov *et al.*, 2020); *Cheilosia candida* Vujić et Radenković, 2020, *Paragus thracusi* Radenković, Likov et Vujić, 2020, and *Psilota aegeae* Vujić, Ståhls et Smit, 2020 (Radenković *et al.*, 2020a); *Merodon olympius* Vujić et Radenković, 2020 (in Radenković *et al.*, 2020b); *Merodon rojoi* Radenković et Vujić, 2020 (Šašić Zorić *et al.*, 2020); *Merodon medium* Vujić, Likov et Radenković, 2020, and *Merodon opacus* Vujić, Likov et Radenković, 2020 (Vujić *et al.*, 2020a); *Merodon chrysotrichos* Vujić, Radenković et Likov, 2020, *Merodon confinium* Šašić Zorić et Vujić, 2020, and *Merodon spineus* Vujić, Šašić Zorić et Likov, 2020 (Vujić *et al.*, 2020b); and *Merodon calidus* Šašić Zorić, Ačanski et Vujić, 2020 (in Vujić *et al.*, 2020d). In the monograph study “Atlas of the hoverflies of Greece” (Vujić *et al.*, 2020c; heretofore referred to as “the Atlas”) all these species were presented under the chapter ‘Syrphid species accounts’ with data on distribution, preferred habitat and biology, but without any morphological or taxonomic information. Regrettably, within the Reference list of the Atlas, original publications were cited with the incorrect year of publishing because, at that time (in 2019) these publications had been accepted, but were only published later on in 2020. A similar case happened with the Atlas. The publisher first gave the following online information: Brill’s Biology E-Books Online, Collection 2019-2020, is the electronic version of the book publication program of Brill in the field of biology for 2019 and 2020 (Brill, 2020b); E-Book (PDF) Publication Date: 11.11.2019; Hardback Publication Date: 11.12.2019 (Brill, 2020a). However, in the hard copy of the Atlas, only 2020 was mentioned as the publishing year, without the exact date.

According to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature, 1999), if the day of publication is not specified in a work, “the earliest day on which the work is demonstrated to be in existence as a published work is to be adopted as the date of publication, but in the absence of such evidence the date to be adopted is the last day of the month, when month and year, but not day, are specified or demonstrated (paragraph 21.3.1.), or the last day of the year when only the year is

specified or demonstrated (paragraph 21.3.2.)". If we accept the hard copy as the source, the day of publication should be 31.12.2020.

To avoid possible misinterpretation of the correct date of publishing and the authority of newly described species regarding principle of priority, here we provide corrected citations of the respective species as follows:

Cheilosia candida Vujić et Radenković, 2020 was published on 12.08.2020 in Radenković *et al.* (2020a) (in the Atlas cited as *Cheilosia candida* Vujić);

Merodon calidus Šašić Zorić, Ačanski et Vujić, 2020 was published on 30.11.2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020d) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon calidus* Vujić, Ačanski et Šašić);

Merodon chrysotrichos Vujić, Radenković et Likov, 2020 published on 08.05.2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020b) (in the Atlas as *Merodon chrysotrichos* Vujić, Radenković et Likov);

Merodon longisetus Vujić, Radenković et Likov, 2020 was published on 08.01.2020 in Likov *et al.* (2020) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon longisetus* Vujić, Radenković et Likov, 2019);

Merodon olympius Vujić et Radenković, 2020 was published on 25.05.2020 in Radenković *et al.* (2020b) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon olympius* Vujić et Radenković);

Merodon opacus Vujić, Likov et Radenković, 2020 was published on 05.02.2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020a) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon opacus* Vujić, Likov et Radenković);

Merodon rojoi Radenković et Vujić, 2020 was published on 29.02.2020 in Šašić Zorić *et al.* (2020) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon rojoi* Radenković et Vujić, 2019);

Merodon spineus Vujić, Šašić Zorić et Likov, 2020 was published on 08.05.2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020b) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon spineus* Radenković, Likov et Vujić);

Paragus thracusi Radenković, Likov et Vujić, 2020 was published on 12.08.2020 in Radenković *et al.* (2020a) (in the Atlas cited as *Paragus thracusi* Radenković et Vujić);

Psilota aegeae Vujić, Ståhls et Smit, 2020 was published on 12.08.2020 in Radenković *et al.* (2020a) (in the Atlas cited as *Psilota aegeae* Vujić, Ståhls et Smit).

Additionally, the name of two *Merodon* species should be corrected due to the masculine gender of the genus name. The specific epithet in accordance with it should be ended by -us not -um:

Merodon confinius Šašić Zorić et Vujić, 2020 was published as *Merodon confinium* on 08.05.2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020b) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon confinium* Šašić et Vujić);

Merodon medius Vujić, Likov et Radenković, 2020 was published as *Merodon medium* on 05.02.2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020a) (in the Atlas cited as *Merodon medium* Vujić, Likov et Radenković).

Furthermore, in the paper of Vujić *et al.* (2020d), due to journal rules the names of authors of the species were shortened to Šašić *et al.* Referring to the ZooBank submission (Pyle, 2019), we propose the correct citations for these three new species of the *Merodon aureus* subgroup:

Merodon albidus Šašić Zorić, Ačanski et Vujić, 2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020d);

Merodon calidus Šašić Zorić, Ačanski et Vujić, 2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020d);

Merodon ortus Šašić Zorić, Ačanski et Vujić, 2020 in Vujić *et al.* (2020d).

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ПРАВИЛНО ЦИТИРАЊЕ НЕДАВНО ОПИСАНИХ ВРСТА РОДОВА *MERODON*, *CHEILOSIA* И *PARAGUS* (DIPTERA: SYRPHIDAE)

АНТЕ ВУЈИЋ, ЛАУРА ЛИКОВ И СНЕЖАНА РАДЕНКОВИЋ

Извод

У раду се наводи правилно цитирање 14 врста описаних у 2020. години које су истовремено наведене у Атласу врста осоликих мува Грчке. У циљу превенције потенцијалних дилема и другачијих таксономских интерпретација у складу са правилима Међународне уније за зоолошку номенклатуру је наведено како треба цитирати 14 приказаних врста.

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